

“INNOVATIVE TEACHING METHODS: COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING”

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13164821>

Abstract: The last century has witnessed a major focus on language teaching as an overall professional section in the education sector. However, the concept “method” was the bottleneck, and the main focus of this concept and consequently got the most attention. This concept represents the practice of teaching as a research-based and systematic set of teaching practices. In a simple definition, you can call it the way of linking theory with practice. Methods are the teaching systems which is usually fixed with the necessary techniques and practices

Keywords: language teaching, methods, approach, linguists, requirements, materials, communicate, techniques, communicate.

1 INTRODUCTION

Methods are the teaching systems which is usually fixed with the necessary techniques and practices. The 1950s-1980s were considered the century of methods, schools were opened that discussed the methodology of language teaching, and other methods appeared among these schools. For example, Silent Way, Suggestopedia, Communicative language teaching, and Total Physical Response. Communicative language teaching (CLT) is closer to the term approach than to methods, and is considered one of the methods used to innovate.

A natural approach is collaborative language learning and content-based learning. Nowadays, the ability to communicate effectively in a foreign language has become the main goal of many language programs around the world. Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) is a method of teaching "what it means to know a language and how to use that knowledge to communicate with people in a variety of settings and situations." The word "innovation" is often used to describe a "new" or "improved" product or development, but only when successfully implemented. (De Lano et al., 1994). Accordingly, innovation includes four main terms: 1. Change, 2. Development, 3. Innovation, 4. Improvement. [3, p. 146].

Traditional teaching methods depended on systematic behavioral analysis of students' pragmatic language learning needs. The Silent Way method was developed by K. Gattenau. He tried to focus more on students and this was one of the bold steps towards innovation. He came to the conclusion that the students should talk more and the teacher should talk less. Computer-assisted language learning did not start out as innovative as many people think. A computer-based language teaching program created in the 1960s focused

on the grammatical and lexical aspects of language teaching. Another important method in language learning is Communicative Language Teaching. The CLT method appeared in Europe in the 1970s in order to make language teaching meet the communicative and functional requirements of students. Its roots lie in changes in British language teaching traditions, and it adopted the Situational Language Method. It was founded by a group of English linguists and applied linguists, and among them the most prominent name in the early stages was the name of Wilkins, who was one of the first to use the term "communicative approach" (1974). CLT aims to make "communicative competence" the goal of language teaching and develop procedures for teaching the four language skills, which include listening, speaking, reading, and writing. In the CLT class, the teacher is a facilitator and consultant. First, they establish a communicative task. Then, students give advice and encouragement as they complete the task. They can also be partners in a task. [2, p. 272].

2 METHODS

8 reasons teachers should use CLT:

1. It's real!

Advocates of the CLT approach highlight that it is just as important for students to just try to speak the language instead of learning key grammatical constructs by rote. They believe that languages are skills that are designed to be used and that learners are not just learning to simply acquire knowledge. CLT educators therefore specifically focus on giving students the skills to clearly and confidently communicate in real-world situations with native speakers of their target language, whether that's in written or spoken form. By communicating real meaning in real-life situations,

learners' natural strategies for language acquisition are triggered. In doing so, students are increasingly motivated to learn – so if you're struggling to get your students engaged using a CLT approach is certainly worth experimenting with.

2. Working with authentic language learning materials

Of course, it's only possible to simulate real-life language situations in the classroom with authentic source materials. It's essential to use genuine content (e.g newspapers, timetables, menus, podcasts, etc.) as part of a CLT approach so that students can easily see the similarity between the classroom activities and the real world. Such materials give students (particularly at higher ability levels) exposure to unregulated native-speaker language and text. They genuinely show the language as it is used by native speakers communicating with other native speakers and can therefore be really helpful in teaching language conventions.

3. Personal experience matters.

For your students, nothing is as real to them as their own lives and lived experience. CLT classrooms are therefore characterised by the extensive use of learners' backgrounds and current situations (e.g looking for work, finding friends, starting a new hobby, etc.), all of which are considered as invaluable contributions to the lesson's content. For those language teachers who pride themselves on forming deep bonds with their students, the CLT method can be a powerful way to engage and support learners. Everyone in the classroom can practice forming questions by finding out information from their peers. And perhaps the combined wisdom of the classroom could help resolve some of the challenges international students might be facing.

4. CLT is a student-centred learning method.

CLT lessons prioritise the use of teaching techniques that require learners to respond to real-world environments and situations. Group and pair work are therefore particularly relevant and widely-used activities to bring language learning to life. Having explained the key concepts in each lesson, the role of the language teacher is to provide scenarios in which students can practice what they have learned and understood. Students are therefore encouraged to spend most of the lesson communicating with their peers – through role plays that are guided but unscripted or through dilemmas and puzzles that need language and communication skills to solve.

5. Get creative.

Clearly this type of lesson requires more thought than simply getting students to learn something by rote. But they also therefore offer opportunities for teachers to demonstrate their creativity and to take risks in

generating original and entertaining ways to engage students. If you're the type of teacher who enjoys creating lessons like this, then CLT is an approach you should definitely try! Your creativity will provide unique ways for students to maximise hands-on practice and to display their understanding of the key points through their communication.

6. Makes writing tasks more engaging for students.

Writing is often a difficult skill for language educators to teach and for students to master. It's also usually a solo activity, conducted in silence and as such is perhaps not that attractive as a classroom activity. Indeed for many educators, a writing task is often used as a piece of homework, although most people don't actually write anything longer than a shopping list in their everyday lives. Making writing more purposeful and writing for a real audience can be powerful ways to use CLT techniques to improve students' engagement with and attainment in writing tasks. And if you look hard enough, there's no shortage of willing readers – e.g other educators, student peers or local communities – or of channels for students to use including newsletters, blogs or social media sites.

7. Develops students' reading skills.

Developing students' reading skills is of vital importance for all language educators and can make a significant difference to their lives. To communicate effectively in their target language, students will need to be able to understand a wide range of written material such as local council communications, public notices, emails from their bank, tax demands and residency information. In an excellent blog post (<https://www.teachingenglish.org.uk/article/making-reading-communicative>) on the topic, the British Council identifies how to develop 'pre-reading', 'while-reading' and 'post-reading' stages and tasks. These leverage the core principles of the CLT approach to make reading more communicative, more engaging and more relevant for learners. Every language learner would benefit from improving their literacy skills in this way.

8. Accuracy vs. Fluency.

There are few more contentious debates in staff rooms than the arguments which rage over whether accuracy is more important than fluency (<https://sanako.com/accuracy-or-fluency>) or vice-versa. If you're a member of Team Fluency, then using a CLT approach in your classroom could be a great idea! The CLT approach believes that errors in language use are entirely natural. It recognises that even native speakers don't always communicate with grammatical perfection all the time! CLT lessons therefore prioritise building

learners' fluency of communication rather than their accuracy. This enables students to build competence gradually and naturally with increased exposure and use. [4, p. 73].

In addition, it was noted that the use of new technologies allows for smooth and fast facilitation of training programs that are highly dependent on communication and simulation. (Nuritdinova et al., 2016). Another interesting proposal suggested that there are several techniques that support and encourage active learning:

- Use of visual media during the lesson (video, PowerPoint pictures);
- Teaching students to take notes during the lesson;
- Use of smartphones or computers during lectures or classes;
- Giving students the opportunity to solve problems during the case study assignment;
- Use of simulation and drilling;
- Development of cooperative teaching methods.

Innovation can also be achieved by making learning opportunities open to humans. This can be done by increasing interaction and reducing the perceptual mismatch between what is intended and what is understood. Integrating language skills can also be one of the key improvements in teaching strategies. As we have seen before, traditional approaches tried to maintain the teacher's prestige at a high level, while the innovative approach ensures students' independence, increases cultural awareness and ensures social importance.

Difficulties in applying an innovative approach:

It is assumed that the ability of teachers to teach in a communicative and innovative way will be difficult due to the lack of experience in this field. Most of the teachers do not have enough skills to communicate fluently with the students. In many cases, teachers were not aware of new innovative methods. In this regard, it is sometimes emphasized that traditions play a certain role.

3 CONCLUSIONS

Research shows that when teachers are faced with the everyday realities of working with real students in real classrooms, they interpret methodology in a variety of ways, which can often include traditional and "teacher-fronted" elements, and they do. Andon and Eckerth (2009), for example, found not only that teachers' beliefs and choices were influenced by requirements to respond to what was happening in their classrooms on a lesson-by-lesson basis, but also that a range of conflicting beliefs held by the teachers could exert an influence on pedagogical decisions. In most of the schools, there are tens of thousands of foreign

language teachers and their supervisors who are awake or will soon be awake, to the job we face. Most of them are frightened, or at best very diffident because they know better than anyone else how ill-equipped they are to do what is expected of them, and how long it takes to become properly equipped in the foreign language skills they need. [5, p. 125].

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